

**Molecular docking and quantum chemical calculation of 4-[(2, 4- dichlorophenyl) amino] 2-
methylidene 4-oxo butanoic acid by density functional theory**

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Abstract

4-[(2,4- dichlorophenyl) amino] 2-methylidene 4-oxo butanoic acid (DPAB) is regarded as an attractive anti viral agent. To rationalize the detailed interaction between DPAB and its inhibitors at the atomic level, an integrated computational approach by combining molecular mechanics and quantum mechanics methods was employed in this report. The spectroscopic properties of 4-[(2,4-dichlorophenyl) amino] 2-methylidene 4-oxo butanoic acid compound were investigated by FT-IR, FT-Raman spectroscopic techniques. FT-IR (4000-400cm⁻¹) and FT-Raman spectra (3500-10cm⁻¹) in the solid phase were recorded. The structural and spectroscopic data of the molecule have been obtained from DFT (B3LYP) with 6-311++G(d,p) and 6-311+G(d,p) basis set calculations. The geometry of the molecule was fully optimized, vibrational spectra were calculated and fundamental vibrations were assigned on the basis of potential energy distribution (PED) of the vibrational modes. Besides, frontier molecular orbitals (FMO), the molecular electrostatic potential (MEP), nonlinear optical properties (NLO) and Fukui functions were performed.